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EVALUATION OF ANTI-OBESITY EFFECT OF SUGOLESS, A NEW POLYHERBAL FORMULATION IN PROGESTERONE INDUCED OBESITY IN MICE

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ABSTRACT

Sugoleless is a natural formulation used for its anti-diabetic properties. It is an herbal medicine for the control of blood sugar. The aim of the study is "Evaluation of Anti-obesity Effect of Sugoleless, A New Polyherbal Formulation in Progesterone Induced Obesity in Mice". The extracts were prepared by maceration method. Anti-obesity activity was evaluated by different parameters like Food intake, Bodyweight, organ weight & relative organ weight, Exploratory behavior, Biochemical estimations & Histopathological examinations. After performing the experiment, it has been concluded that the sugoleless formulation has anti-obesity properties, sugoleless formulation of 1480 mg/kg showed better activity than 740 mg/kg and 370 mg/kg ($p < 0.05$).

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INTRODUCTION

HERBAL MEDICINE

Herbal medicines are the Natural substances derived from plants which are used to cure diseases in traditional, local or regional medicine. These substances are unique blends of organic compounds that can originate from any unprocessed or refined portion of a plant. Every civilization in the world has used herbal medicine at one time or another. Traditional medical systems come in a wide variety, and while each one's philosophy and methods are impacted by social factors, environmental factors, and geographical factors, they all have a holistic outlook on life. There should be a focus on health rather than disease, according to well-known herbal medicine systems as Traditional Chinese Medicine and Ayurvedic Medicine. People can prosper and concentrate on their general health instead of a specific illness that typically results from an out of balance mind, body, and environment by taking therapeutic herbs. The use of herbal medicine dates back to early civilizations. It entails the use of plants as medicines to cure illness and improve people's overall health and wellness. Herbal medicine, commonly referred to as herbalism or botanical medicine, is a type of treatment that relies on the application or ingestion of plant materials to treat illness. Because pharmacists and doctors are learning about traditional knowledge, herbal medicine has been used for many years by many different cultures across the world to cure diseases like malaria, warts, bowel disorders, heart conditions, and chronic pain. Over 25 percent of total of medicines given globally are made from plants. 11 percent of the 252 medications on the World Health Organization's list of essential medicines are solely derived from plants. In fact, opium derived from poppies' seed pods was used to make the first pharmacological compound, morphine, some 200 years ago. Since then, researchers have been investigating plants to develop the modern pharmaceuticals we are familiar with. But people are starting to pay more attention to natural, herbal treatment after years of overmedicating, dealing with resistant bacteria in the microbiome, and treating the symptoms rather than the cause of the problem. [1,2]

Today, plants are utilized to treat a variety of health issues and disorders, such as allergies, arthritis, migraines, exhaustion, skin infections, wounds, burns, gastrointestinal problems, and even cancer, demonstrating that food truly is medicine. Many individuals are returning to this more conventional form of care because these herbs are less expensive and a safer form of treatment than standard pharmaceuticals. Despite being used for thousands of years, botanical medicine is still useful in the present, Western world. According to a recent estimate by the World Health Organization, 80 percent of people worldwide rely on herbal medicines for some aspect of their primary healthcare, and the global market for these products is close to \$60 billion annually. Due to the rising cost of pharmaceutical drugs and the resurgence of interest in natural or organic treatments, there has been an increase in interest in herbal therapy among people.[3]

INDIAN HERBAL MARKET

India has the potential to dominate the worldwide market for herbal-based medicines. By 2010, exports of herbal products and pharmaceuticals might increase from approximately Rs. 456 crores to Rs. 10,000 crores. The present market for nutraceuticals, or "health foods," which include herbal medications, is projected to be between \$80 to \$250 billion in the USA and Europe. The following are the criteria for choosing plants for research on herbal medications for different types of human illnesses.

- Real use of medicinal plants in the region's countries.
- scientific literature supporting the plants' therapeutic value for specific diseases.
- The plants are mentioned as having healing properties in ancient literature.
- The therapeutic use of medicinal plants in nations outside the region.

The first World Congress of Clinical Pharmacology and Therapeutics was held in London in 1980 to investigate plants that might have medicinal effects. The following steps make up the standard research methodology for herbal drugs.

- Identification of the plant reportedly in use.
- Collection of the plant.
- Transport of the plant to the research laboratory.
- Storage of the plant.
- Preparation of the extracts.
- Toxicity studies of the plant extracts in animals.
- Evaluation of therapeutic efficacy of the extract in animal models.
- Identification of the extracts which is having more activities.
- Further fractionation of the active molecule.
- Structural elucidation of the bio-active molecule.
- Synthesis of bio-active molecule.

The markets of developed nations are currently flooded with phytomedicines, and consumers around the world have indicated a preference for formulations made from natural herbs. The pharmaceutical industry in the West has exhibited a renewed dedication to looking for new therapeutic compounds from higher plants since the development of automated high-throughput screening techniques. Some plants with gastro protective properties include *Solanum torvum*, *Toona ciliata*, *Ocimum suave*, *Rhizopora mangle L* and *Asparagus racemosus*. [4]

TRADITIONAL HERBAL MEDICINES AND PUBLIC HEALTH CARE IN INDIA

Communities all throughout the world continue to use and abide by the age-old traditional medical methods. India continues to make outstanding contributions to the development of conventional healthcare systems. The current study examines the potency of India's ancient medical practices and its medicinal plants, which not only have contributed to health care since the beginning of time but are also the community's top choice for treating a variety of chronic ailments. For the purpose of compiling data on the traditional medical systems used in India, including Ayurveda, Unani, homoeopathy, and Siddha, a thorough literature review was conducted. One of the earliest medical systems to have developed in India is Ayurveda, according to a comprehensive analysis of the available data. It is a comprehensive system of care that combines a regular diet, the use of medication, and adhering to rituals like exercise and behavior. Around 6,500 plant species are known to occur in India and are employed by many streams of traditional health care practitioners. Plants play a key role in Indian systems of medicine as the raw material for medical formulations.[5]

OBESITY

Obesity is described as the condition of having too much fat in the body due to an imbalance in caloric intake and expenditure. It is one of the main causes of non-communicable diseases such type 2 diabetes, hypertension, cardiovascular disorders, and even cancer. [6,7] In 1997, the World Health Organization (WHO) identified obesity as a significant global public health issue [8]. Due to recent changes in eating habits and physical activity patterns, obesity has become more common. Those who have a BMI (Body mass index) between 25 to 29.5 are regarded as overweight, and those who have a BMI of 30 or higher are regarded as obese. Anti-obesity medications, however, are a typical adjuvant because these interventions have poor long-term success and the burden is regained when therapy is stopped . [9]

Over time, a variety of medications have been utilized to treat obesity. Yet, the majority of the weight loss medications that were approved and sold have since been discontinued due to serious side effects. Fenfluramine and dexfenfluramine were taken off the market in the 1990s due to heart valve damage. [10]

Due to an unacceptable chance to benefit ratio, the European Medicines Agency (EMA) approved the market withdrawal of many anti-obesity medications in 2000, including phentermine, diethylpropion, and mazindol. [11] Rimonabant, the main selective cb1 receptor blocker, was made available in 56 foreign countries starting in 2006, however it was never approved by the U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA) due to a higher risk of psychiatric side effects such depression, anxiety, and suicide ideation. Rimonabant was ultimately taken off the market in Europe in 2009. [12]

The ideal anti-obesity disorders medication might result in sustained weight loss with the fewest side effects. The mechanisms that modify power balance are influenced by social, hedonic, and mental factors that limit the efficacy of pharmacological therapies. They also have a substantial amount of built-in redundancy and significantly overlap with other physiological capacities. So, it should come as no surprise that anti-obesity concerns drug discovery programmed have been riddled with false starts, failures during clinical development, and withdrawals due to side effects that were no longer fully favored at the time of release. Tablets that target metabolic pathways in tissues such adipocytes, the liver, and skeletal muscle have demonstrated efficacy in preclinical research, but none have yet entered the clinical development stage. Recent advances in our understanding of leptin and its upstream pathways in the hypothalamus, as well as peptidergic signalling of hunger and satiety from the gastrointestinal tract mediated by ghrelin, cholecystokinin (CCK), peptide YY (PYY), and glucagon-like peptide-1 (GLP-1), have opened up new possibilities. Whilst a few have now advanced to the trial stage, it is incredibly doubtful if they will clear the demanding regulatory requirements necessary for licensing an anti-obesity drug. Yet, GLP-1 receptor agonists have already been successful in treating diabetes, and because of the favorable results they have on people's body weight, they may also lead the way for new anti-obesity medications. It is evident that a new paradigm is required to produce medications that control frame weight to the amount visible after surgical procedure. Reduced doses of a few medicines focused on several healing pathways can frequently produce better results than methods that only affect one pathway in conditions like diabetes and hypertension. Whilst certain peptide and small molecule combinations have now entered the clinical trial stage, recent regulatory experience reveals that there are still significant obstacles to overcome. In the future, the effectiveness safety and sustainability of weight reduction of this multitherapeutic approach may one day compete with surgical treatment.[13] Current clinical trials with excellent therapeutic options, such as GLP-1 receptor (GLP1R) agonism, are promoting hope that novel, drug-based treatment of weight issues may also be feasible. On June 4, 2021, the US Food and Drug Administration (FDA) approved semaglutide 2.4 mg for use in connection with a reduced-calorie, weight loss programmed and increased physical activity in adults with weight problems or obese adults with at least one weight-related condition (such as high blood pressure, cholesterol, or T2D). This is currently the second GLP1R agonist approved for body weight control, following the FDA's approval of liraglutide 3 mg in 2014 for the treatment of individual weight problems and in 2020 for the treatment of weight problems in adolescents aged 12 to 17 years . [14] Actually, complex interplay between genetic, environmental, socioeconomic, and nutritional factors ultimately lead to obesity. The conventional theories of weight gain no longer fully explain the rate of increase of excess weight in westernized or socioeconomically developed nations. Antibiotic exposure and other lifestyle factors, particularly in the early years of life, that may also be linked to epigenetic modifications are being investigated as potential risk factors for weight problems in later life. Low-grade inflammation, altered microbiota, and increased endocannabinoid system tone are all signs of weight difficulties.

The Process of Obese Signaling Pathways

Obesity folks secrete muchless adiponectin then lean individuals. The diminished production of adiponectin, in aggregate with the lack of ability of adipose tissue to save the surplus free fatty acids (FFAs), can be regarded to mirror adipose tissue dysfunction. Under regular conditions, adiponectin will increase insulin sensitivity directly, by way of stimulating tyrosine phosphorylation of the insulin receptor. Adiponectin, binding to adipo-receptor R1/R2, can prompt 5'-AMP-activated protein kinase (AMPK), leading to improved fatty acid oxidation and diminished inflow of FFAs into the liver. Independent of AMPK activation, adiponectin decreases the production of reactive oxygen species (ROS), which may additionally end result in reduced activation of mitogen-activated-protein-kinase (MAPK) and thereby inhibition of cell proliferation.

FFAs signaling pathway

FFAs are accelerated in obesity and are implicated as proximate reasons of insulin resistance and induction of inflammatory signaling in adipose, liver, muscle, and pancreas. Cells of the innate immune device produce cytokines and different elements that have an effect on insulin signaling and end result in the development of insulin resistance which is often viewed in obesity. Obesity induces lipolysis and launch of pro-inflammatory FFAs and factors, such as tumor necrosis factor alpha (TNF- α). TNF- α initiates signaling via tumor necrosis factor receptor 1 (TNFR1) with the consequent regulation of gene expression, recruiting TNFR1-associated dying area (TRADD), TNF receptor-associated factor-2 (TRAF2), and receptor-interacting protein (RIP). They then result in TGF β -activated kinase 1 (TAK1) and TAK1-TAB complicated which prompts NF- κ B critical modulator (NEMO), IKK α , and IKK β , inhibiting insulin receptor substrate (IRS). The activation of the I κ Bkinase leads to phosphorylation of I κ B and launch of NF- κ B, which then translocates to the nucleus and binds to the promoters of pro-inflammatory genes and initiates transcription.

Route for insulin signalling

When insulin binds to the insulin receptor (IR), the receptor's tyrosine kinase is activated and receptor phosphorylation, allowing docking proteins like insulin receptor substrates to bind (IRS). Through a number of downstream signaling networks, including as the phosphatidylinositol 3-kinase (PI3K)-AKT system, mammalian target of rapamycin (mTOR), and the MAPK systems, it then enhances cell proliferation.

Signaling through SFAs

The majority of fats, including lauric, myristic, palmitic, and stearic acids, are saturated fatty acids (SFAs). They can activate the myeloid differentiation primary response protein 88 (MyD88)-TIR-domain-containing adapter-inducing interferon- β (TRIF)-dependent pathway by binding to Fetuin-A, an endogenous ligand of toll-like receptor 2 (TLR2) or TLR4 and starting the transcription of interferon regulatory factor 3 (IRF3). Ubiquitinligase called TNF receptor-associated factor-3 (TRAF3) is enlisted to both MYD88 and TRIF-assembled signalling complexes. IRF3 is activated by the IKK-related kinases (TBK1) and IKK, and after activation, IRF3 moves into the nucleus and binds to specific DNA sequences. [15,16]

Obesity causes include:

1. Food or behavior
2. The local environment
3. Genetics
4. Other disease

1.)Food or behavior

Good eating habits and frequent exercise are examples of healthy behaviour. In order to avoid gaining too much weight, it's important to maintain an energy balance between the calories taken from food and drink and the calories used by the body during activity. The American Dietary Guidelines, which place an emphasis on eating whole grains, fruits, vegetables, lean protein, low-fat and fat-free dairy products, and drinking water, form the basis of a healthy diet pattern. For long-term health advantages and the prevention of chronic diseases like type 2 diabetes and heart diseases, it's also crucial to maintain a healthy food pattern and engage in regular physical exercise.

2.)The local environment

Due to a lack of sidewalks or secure bike trails, a person may decide against biking or walking to the store or to their work place. Environments such as a person's home, place of employment, and daycare centre might affect their everyday behavior.

3.)Genetics

The human population experiences genetic changes too slowly for them to be the cause of the increase in obesity. However, the differences in how individuals react to a setting that encourages inactivity and consumption of high-calorie meals raises the possibility that genes do play a part in the formation of obesity. The body receives instructions from the genes on how to react to changes in its surroundings. Rarely is a precise mutation of a single gene responsible for a family's evident pattern of inherited obesity.

4.) Other disease

Obesity or weight increase can result from certain conditions. This can include polycystic ovarian syndrome and Cushing's disease. The use of medications like steroids and some antidepressants might result in weight gain. The evidence on other factors, such as chemical exposures and the impact of the microbiome, in energy balance and weight growth is still developing. In order to determine whether behaviours, illnesses, medications, and/or psychological issues are causing weight gain or making it difficult to lose weight, a health care practitioner can help you learn more about your health habits and history.[17]

Classification For Management of Obesity

Nonpharmacological Treatment

1.) Diet and Behavior Modification

An integrated programme of calorie and fat restriction, exercise, and behaviour change is the basis of obesity management. A 5% to 10% loss from starting weight should be the initial weight loss target. Dietary advice may be extremely important for patient compliance, particularly in the first year of weight loss. A net caloric deficit of 500 to 1,000 kcal per day is necessary for a healthy weight loss of one to two pounds per week. There are two methods to accomplish this net deficit: by consuming fewer calories or by using more calories than you consume. The National Heart, Lung, and Blood Institute recommends engaging in physical activity for 30 to 45 minutes, three to five days per week.

2.) Surgical Options

When diet, exercise, and medication therapy have not yielded satisfying results, bariatric surgery is a possibility. Numerous comorbid disorders, including diabetes, hypertension, lipid abnormalities, obstructive sleep apnea, and female urinary stress incontinence, have been proven to improve with weight loss obtained by bariatric surgery. Patients who meet the requirements for surgery must have a BMI of 40 kg/m² or greater, and the advantages of the procedure should exceed the disadvantages. Patients with a BMI of 35 kg/m² or above with a comorbidity such as severe diabetes, sleep apnea, or joint illness may also be candidates for surgery, according to the National Institutes of Health (NIH). The Centers for Medicare and Medicaid Services (CMS) approved weight-loss surgery reimbursement for patients in February 2006[13]. Gastric restriction, malabsorption, or a combination of the two methods can also result in weight loss after surgery. Procedures like the vertical banded gastroplasty and the laparoscopic adjustable band fall under the category of gastric restriction. When it comes to weight loss, gastric bypass uses both methods, but biliopancreatic diversion with duodenal switch uses a method that causes malabsorption. Due to low satisfaction rates, vertical banded gastroplasty, which was common in the 1980s, has been overtaken by alternatives.[18]

3.) Duodenal switch

The duodenal switch, which involves removing two-thirds of the stomach and bypassing the majority of the small intestine, is another surgical procedure that is growing in popularity in the United States. It is the bariatric procedure that is the most traumatic. Similar to a gastric bypass, this operation causes early weight reduction, but patients continue to lose weight two years after surgery, and the average amount of weight lost is substantially higher. The dangers of the duodenal switch include malnutrition, increased bowel motions, and nutritional deficits. Patients who choose bariatric surgery must be very committed to making changes in their food and lifestyle.[19]

Pharmacological Treatments

Orlistat

Until 2012, the only FDA-approved anti-obesity medication was orlistat. Since 2007, this medication has been sold over-the-counter in the United States after first receiving approval in 1990. An enzyme called lipase, which is made in the pancreas and stomach and aids in converting triglycerides to fatty acids, is inhibited by orlistat. As a result, the rate of fat absorption is reduced by almost 30%. Flatulence and steatorrhea are the two main adverse effects of orlistat, however other side effects like nephrotoxicity, hepatotoxicity, kidney stones, and pancreatitis have also been recorded. The majority of studies found that orlistat had a 30% overall median discontinuation rate.[20]

Lorcaserin

Serotonin receptors have emerged as new targets for research into anti-obesity medications as a result of the discovery that serotonin plays a significant role in satiety and hence limits hunger. The satiety centre, which is found in the ventromedial nucleus of the hypothalamus, and the hunger centre, which is situated in the lateral hypothalamus, regulate food intake. Two different types of neurons that regulate food intake are located in the arcuate nucleus, where many inputs from higher regions and gastrointestinal tracts converge. Agouti-related protein and neuropeptide Y are produced by the first food intake group, and cocaine and amphetamine regulated transcript (CART) and pro-opiomelanocortin (POMC) neurons are found in the second food intake inhibitory group. The 5-HT_{2C} receptors found in POMC release alpha-melanocyte stimulating hormone when they are activated. Paraventricular nucleus of the hypothalamus is further projected by both inhibitory and stimulatory neurons. The melanocyte 4 receptors (MC4R) found in the paraventricular nucleus suppress appetite. When used in therapeutic levels, lorcaserin acts on POMC neurons as a selective 5-HT_{2C} agonist, resulting in the release of alpha MSH. Moreover, alpha MSH affects MC4R in the paraventricular nucleus of the hypothalamus, which results in a reduction in appetite. Lorcaserin also affects 5-HT_{2B} and 5-HT_{2A} receptors at supratherapeutic levels. Initially appearing to be more helpful, lorcaserin gradually loses its capacity to sustain long-term weight loss. This medicine lowers total cholesterol and triglyceride levels but does not lower LDL cholesterol or HDL cholesterol.

The potential rise in cancer rates is still a concern. Patients who need anti-obesity treatment for a brief period of time may choose this medication, as can women who have no recognised risk factors for breast cancer.[21]

Phentermine/Topiramate

Phentermine is a sympathomimetic amine anorectic. It works in a manner similar to amphetamine in that it acts as an agonist at the TAAR1 receptor site, causing norepinephrine and epinephrine to be released. It stimulates the central nervous system.

Topiramate is an anticonvulsant that lowers the seizure threshold while stabilizing the membrane by acting on voltage-gated sodium and calcium channels and enhancing GABA-A receptors. Topiramate antagonizes glutamate receptors in addition to being a mild carbonic anhydrase inhibitor. Based on the combination of the above mechanisms, topiramate enhances satiety enhancement and appetite suppression.

Those who are at risk for developing anxiety or depression or who have such conditions currently are not advised to take this drug. Patients who are female and taking oral contraceptives while taking this combination need to be counselled about the possibility of diminished contraceptive efficacy. Patients who require weight loss and additionally experience fatigue, nerve pain, or muscle pain would benefit from this combination.[22]

Naltrexone/bupropion

The FDA authorized bupropion/naltrexone in 2014. This combination drug's exact mode of action is not yet fully known. An opioid receptor antagonist called naltrexone is used to treat alcohol and drug addiction. Bupropion is an antidepressant that also contributes in weight loss and the promotion of quitting smoking respectively. The selective dopamine and noradrenalin re-uptake inhibitor bupropion reduces cravings for food and nicotine, possibly by raising the extracellular dopamine level. This combination reduces hunger but has no impact on how the body uses energy. Compared to orlistat, this combination offers more weight loss while having less adverse effects. Those who smoke and have mild to moderate depression might consider this medicine.[23]

Liraglutide

The only injectable weight reduction drug currently on the market that has received FDA approval is liraglutide. With 97% amino acid similarity to human endogenous GLP-1, liraglutide is a long-acting counterpart of GLP-1. The position 34 of native GLP-1 was changed to arginine from lysine to obtain this 97% homology. Dipeptidyl peptidase-4 (DPP-4) breaks down endogenous GLP-1 quickly, and its insulin action is transient. A fatty acid molecule included in liraglutide binds to albumin and increases the structure's half-life. Pancreatic alpha and beta cells, the central and peripheral neurological systems, the heart, lungs, and gastrointestinal (GI) tract all have GLP-1 receptors. Liraglutide stimulates the release of insulin when blood glucose levels are raised via the messenger intracellular cyclic adenosine monophosphate (cAMP). Liraglutide also reduces glucagon secretion and postpones stomach emptying due to receptor sites. More weight is lost with liraglutide than with a placebo. Hypoglycemia is one of the main adverse effects of this medicine. Patients with hyperglycemia or overt diabetes find it particularly alluring, while those at risk for hypoglycemia should stay away from it. Those who require higher levels of HDL cholesterol and lower levels of total cholesterol and triglycerides would also benefit from using this medicine.[24]

Reason behind Choosing the plant-based medicines are: -

- Adverse effects like gastric lesions, alteration in blood pressure, suicidal thoughts etc., are not there in herbal medicines.
- Plant based drugs used in the traditional medicine have been paid great attention because they are: -
 - * Cheap.
 - * Have little side effects.
- * According to WHO still about 80% of the population mainly on plant Based medicines [25].
- Modern science has been able to isolate some of these compounds from the plants, identifying exactly how they work.
- Treatment of complex cases like cancer, components of plants proved to be very effective.
- It can be synergic, supportive and preventive.

Rational

In day-to-day practice most of the obese patients were treated with standard anti-obesity drugs can produce increase in heart rate and blood pressure, insomnia, constipation and nervousness and thus search for a new safe and potent anti-obesity herbal formulation is essential to overcome these problems. Ayurvedic drugs lacking such side effects and are being searched as alternatives to standard anti-obesity drugs.

Aim and objective of the Study

1. To carry out organoleptic evaluation of polyherbal formulation.
2. To carry out phytochemical studies of polyherbal formulation
3. To carry out Anti-obesity effects of polyherbal formulation.
4. To compare with the standard orlistat at different doses of polyherbal formulation.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Sugolessformulation :-

1. Gudmar (*Gymnema Sylvestre*) 60 mg
 2. Jamunbeej(*Eugenia Jambolana*) 60 mg
 3. Saptaparna(*AlstoniaScholaris*) 70 mg
 4. Methi(*TrigonellaFoenum-Graecum*)30 mg
 5. Karela (*MomordiaCharantia*)40 mg
 6. Mamejwa(*Enicostemma Littorale*)40 mg
 7. Vijaysar(*PterocarpusSantalinus*)40 mg
 8. Bilwapatra(*AegleMarmelos*) 20 mg
 9. Nimbgiri(*Azadirachta Indica*) 20 mg
 10. Arjun (*Terminalia Arjuna*) 20 mg
 11. Giloy(*Tinospora Cordifolia*)20 mg
 12. Haridra (*Curcuma Longa*)20 mg
 13. Amla (*Embelica Officinalis*) 20 mg
 14. Shuddha Shilajit(*Aspathum*) 20 mg
 15. Kadu (*Picrorhiza Kurroa*) 20 mg
- The polyherbal (sugoless) formulation is prepared by mixing the above plants.
- The sugoless formulation is purchased from “Ayucare Pharmaceuticals Ahmedabad, Gujarat”.

Preparation of the extract of mixture component

1. 20g of mixture material was taken in a clean flat glass container.
2. Soaked in 100 ml of solvent system (ethanol and water in proportion of 7:3).
3. The container with its contents was sealed and kept for a period of 3 days.
4. Occasional shaking.
5. Filtration by cotton material then it was filtered through whatman filter paper.
6. The filtrate was evaporated by rotary evaporator.

Powder[Figure:- 1]

Maceration [Figure :- 2]

Filtration [Figure :- 3]

Evaporation. [Figure :- 4]

Preliminary Phytochemical Studies

- Phytochemical screening of the polyherbal formulation extracts was conducted with various qualitative tests to identify the presence of chemical constituents.
- The formulation contains Alkaloids, Cardiac Glycosides, Saponin Glycosides, Flavonoid, Phenolic Compound and Tannins, Carbohydrates, Sterols.

Pharmacognostic Tests

[Table :- 1].

Chemical Components	Test Performed
Alkaloid	Dragendroff's Test
Cardiac Glycoside	Keller Killiani Test
Saponin Glycoside	Foam Test
Flavonoid	Alkaline Reagent Test
Phenolic Compound and Tannins	Ferric Chloride Test
Carbohydrates	Fehling's Test

Keller Killani Test [Figure :- 5].

Fehling's Test [Figure :- 6]

Dragendroff's Test [Figure :- 7]

Alkaline Reagent Test [Figure :- 8]

Foam Test[Figure :- 9]

Ferric Chloride Test [Figure :- 10]

Organoleptic evaluation

Evaluation of the formulation will be done for sensory characteristics such as: -

- Colour, odour, taste, texture, fracture etc.
- For determining the odour small portion of the sample will be placed in the beaker of suitable size.
- They will be examined by slow and repeated inhalation of the air over the material.

Animals required

- Species and Strain: Swiss albino mice.
- Age and Weight: 4-6 months & 25-30 gm.
- Gender: Female.

The animals were kept in stainless steel cages. They housed at an ambient temperature of between 25- 27°C and relative humidity of about 50-55% with free access to feed and water. The study protocol was accepted by the Gupta College of Technological Sciences' ethical committee [Protocol no - GCTS/IAEC/2022/SEPT/03].

The use of BSA (Body surface area) for dose translation

Research will be used BSA for conversion of drug doses between species for many years. The origin for understanding the relationship between the BSA of different species began in 1883 when observations that oxygen utilization and caloric expenditure were similar for various mammalian species and differently sized members of the same species when computed on the basis of body surface. These observations were then confirmed and applied to humans, which gave rise to expressing human basal metabolism in terms of BSA rather than body weight. [26]

Formula for dose translation based on BSA

$$\text{HED (mg/kg)} = \text{Animal Dose (mg/kg)} \times \text{Animal } K_M / \text{Human } K_M$$

Experimental design

Thirty-six female Swiss albino mice will be randomly divided into six groups (n=6) and will treat daily for 28 days. Group I will be received 2% gum acacia (10 ml/kg, p.o.). Group II will be received progesterone (10 mg/kg, s.c), Group III will be received Orlistat (10mg/kg, p.o) 30 min before progesterone administration subcutaneously. Group IV, V and VI will be received Polyherbal Formulation orally at dose of 370 mg/kg, 740 mg/kg and 1480 mg/kg, 30 min before progesterone administration. Progesterone will dissolve in arachis oil and administered subcutaneously in the dorsal neck region.[27]

[Table :- 2]

Sl. No	Group	No of animal	Treatment
1	Group I	6	2% gum acacia (10 ml/kg) P.O
2	Group II	6	progesterone (10 mg/kg) S.C
3	Group III	6	Orlistat (10mg/kg) P.O
4	Group IV	6	PHF (370 mg/kg)P.O
5	Group V	6	PHF(740 mg/kg) P.O
6	Group VI	6	PHF (1480 mg/kg) P.O
Total Number of Animal		36	

Food intake

The effect of Polyherbal formulation on food intake will be recorded on day 1, 7, 14, 21 and 28. The mice will be deprived of food 1 hr prior to experimentation. On these days 10 g of sweetened corn will presented to groups of mice in glass petridishes and food intake will be recorded at 0.5, 1 and 2 hr time intervals. The result will be recorded as average of all the weeks at respective time intervals and amount of food consumed/20 g body weight will be calculated.[28]

Body weight, organ weight and relative organ weight

The body weight of mice will be recorded on day 1 and day 29 using an electronic balance and the % change in their body weight will be calculated. At the end of the experiment mice will sacrifice and liver will be isolated, weighed and relative liver weight will be calculated.

$$\text{Relative liver weight} = (\text{liver weight} / \text{Body weight}) \times 100.[29]$$

Exploratory behavior

On 28th day, post 30 min of drug administration ambulation, grooming and rearing will be noted by means of open field test. The animals will keep under laboratory conditions for one hour prior to the test. Open field test will be performed by placing the mice in the center and ambulatory activity (squares crossed by horizontal movement) as well as frequency of rearing (Standing up vertically) and grooming (face washing and repetitive licks directed to body) will be recorded for five minutes using a camcorder for noting the exact reading and storage of data.[30]

Biochemical estimations

On 29th day blood will withdraw from Sephaneous Vein from over-night fasted mice. Blood will be centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 15 min and serum will be separated. Biochemical parameters like blood glucose (4) total cholesterol (TC) (5), high density lipoprotein (HDL), triglyceride (TG) (6), serum glutamate oxaloacetate transaminase (SGOT), and serum glutamate pyruvate transaminase (SGPT) (7) will be estimated using commercial diagnostic kits by Chem star Biochemical Semi Auto analyzer. Whereas the low-density lipoprotein (LDL) and very low-density lipoprotein (VLDL) levels will calculate according to Friedwald's formula.

$$\text{LDL in mg \%} = \text{Total cholesterol} - \text{HDL-C} - \text{Triglycerides}/5$$

$$\text{VLDL in mg \%} = \text{Triglycerides}/5. [31,32]$$

Histopathological examinations

At the end of experiment mice will be sacrificed by Thiopental Sodium, liver will be isolated and stored in 10% formalin solution. The sections of liver will be stained with haematoxylin and eosin and observed under light microscope (100X). [33]

Statistical analysis

Statistical analysis was done using one way ANOVA followed by Tukey HSD Test. Significance level of $p < 0.05$ was considered as significant. [34]

RESULTS

Preliminary phytochemical analysis ofSugoleess formulation.

The formulation contains Alkaloids, Cardiac Glycosides, Saponin Glycosides, Flavonoid, Phenolic Compound and Tannins, Carbohydrates, Sterols.

[Table :- 3] Organoleptic properties of sugoless formulation.

Test	Sugoless Formulation
Alkaloid	+
Cardiac Glycoside	+
Saponin Glycoside	+
Flavonoid	+
Phenolic Compound and Tannins	+
Carbohydrates	+

[Table :- 4]

Organoleptic properties	Result
Colour	Dull brown
Odour	Characteristic
Taste	Astringent
Appearance	Moderately fine , No clumping or aggregation

Food intake

When compared to normal control mice, the subcutaneous treatment of progesterone (10 mg/kg) to mice for 28 days dramatically enhanced food intake after 2 hours. A substantial decrease in food intake was seen in mice after 0.5 hours following oral administration of Sugoless Formulation (370, 740, and 1480 mg/kg) in comparison to progesterone control mice. Sugoless 1480 mg/kg treated animals showed a significant difference when compared to 370 mg/kg and 740 mg/kg-treated mice. However, administration of orlistat 10 mg/kg followed by progesterone 10 mg/kg produces better result as compared to all the other groups in respect to Food intake in and after 2 hours.

[Table :- 5]

Treatment (mg/kg)	30 min	60 min	120 min
Control	2.33± 0.74	4.50± 0.76	6.50± 0.95
Progesterone(10 mg/kg)	4.16 ± 0.68	6.50± 0.95	10.66± 0.74
Standard (10 mg/kg)	2.50 ±0.76	3.16± 0.68	5.30 ±0.74
PHF (370 mg/kg)	4.00 ± 0.81	5.83± 0.68	8.50± 0.95
PHF (740 mg/kg)	4.30 ± 0.74	6.33± 0.94	7.50± 0.95
PHF (1480 mg/k)	2.33 ± 0.74	4.33 ±0.74	6.50 ±0.95

n = 6 and $p < 0.01$, $p < 0.05$, $p < 0.01$ when compared to standard ; ANOVA followed by Tukey HSD test.

[Figure:- 11]

Fig 3 :- This histogram shows the various responses in mice on food intake in 30 min , 60 min & 120 min after the drug administration, X axis in Time (min). Y axis in Gram (weight of food).

Body weight, liver weight and relative liver weight

When compared to normal control mice, progesterone control mice without treatment showed a considerable rise in body weight. In mice given progesterone injections 10 mg/kg, sugoless formulation treatment at doses of 370 mg/kg, 740 mg/kg, and 1480 mg/kg body weight considerably restored the body weight compared to the progesterone injection control mice that weren't treated. The body weight of the Sugoless Formulation 1480 mg/kg treated mice was likewise significantly different from the Sugoless Formulation 370 mg/kg and 740 mg/kg treated animals. In addition, oral administration of Sugoless Formulation at dose levels of 370 mg/kg, 740 mg/kg, and 1480 mg/kg body weight recovered considerably increased liver weight caused by progesterone injection in comparison to progesterone-treated control mice. However, administration of orlistat 10 mg/kg followed by progesterone 10 mg/kg produces better result as compared to all the other groups in respect to body weight.

[Table :- 6]

Treatment (mg/kg)	Body weight	Liver weight	Relative liver weight
Control	24.50± 1.70	2.16± 0.68	9.00± 2.58
Progesterone(10 mg/kg)	39.50 ± 1.70	2.66± 0.74	6.66± 1.88
Standard (10 mg/kg)	28.33 ± 1.10	1.83± 0.68	6.33±2.56
PHF (370 mg/kg)	36.16 ± 1.34	1.66± 0.74	4.83± 2.19
PHF (740 mg/kg)	32.66 ± 1.49	2.16± 0.68	7.00± 2.44
PHF (1480 mg/kg)	29.50 ± 1.70	1.83 ±0.68	6.50 ±2.36

n =6 and $p < 0.01$, $p < 0.01$, $p < 0.01$ when compared to standard ; ANOVA followed by Tukey HSD test.

Exploratory behaviour

Comparing non-treated progesterone control mice to control mice, it was found that there was a significant reduction in the number of ambulations and rearing as well as an increase in grooming. As compared to progesterone control mice, those given sugoless formulation at doses of 370 mg/kg, 740 mg/kg, and 1480 mg/kg orally for 28 days saw a considerable increase in ambulation, decreased grooming, and increased rearing. However, there was a noticeable difference between the sugoless treatments at 370 mg/kg, 740 mg/kg, and 1480 mg/kg. But administration of orlistat 10 mg/kg followed by progesterone 10 mg/kg produces better result as compared to all the other groups in respect to ambulation, rearing and grooming.

[Table :- 7]

Treatment (mg/kg)	Ambulation	Rearing	Grooming
Control	82.83± 1.34	11.16± 1.06	2.00± 0.81
Progesterone(10 mg/kg)	60.83 ± 2.91	4.50± 0.95	4.33± 0.74
Standard (10 mg/kg)	80.50 ± 1.25	11.00± 0.81	2.16±0.68
PHF (370 mg/kg)	69.00± 1.06	7.83± 0.68	3.16± 0.68
PHF (740 mg/kg)	73.16 ± 1.06	9.16± 0.68	2.16± 0.68
PHF (1480 mg/kg)	78.83 ± 1.34	10.16 ±1.06	2.16 ±0.68

n =6 and $p < 0.01$, $p < 0.01$, $p < 0.02$ when compared to standard ; ANOVA followed by Tukey HSD test.

Biochemical estimations

In comparison to control mice, daily subcutaneous progesterone injection for 28 days significantly increased blood glucose, total cholesterol, triglyceride, LDL, and VLDL levels while considerably lowering HDL. However, compared to progesterone-treated mice, the mice treated with sugoless formulation at dose levels of 370, 740, and 1480 mg/kg body weight significantly reduced the high levels of blood glucose, total cholesterol, triglyceride, LDL, and VLDL and increased HDL. Additionally, 370 mg/kg, 740 mg/kg, and 1480 mg/kg caused a considerably lower blood glucose, total cholesterol, triglyceride, LDL, and VLDL levels in comparison to different concentration of sugoless formulation, although no significant effect was seen in HDL. When compared to non-treated progesterone control mice, the high levels of SGOT and SGPT were dramatically reduced after 28 days of sugoless formulation administration at doses of 370 mg/kg, 740 mg/kg, and 1480 mg/kg. But administration of or list at 10 mg/kg followed by progesterone 10 mg/kg produces better result as compared to all the other groups in respect to all Biochemical parameters.

[Table :- 8]

Biochemical parameters	Control	Progesterone (10 mg/kg)	Standard (10 mg/kg)	PHF (370 mg/kg)	PHF (740 mg/kg)	PHF (1480mg/kg)
Blood glucose (mg/dl)	73.16± 1.46	128.00± 2.58	78.33± 1.10	105.33± 1.10	94.33± 1.10	84.50± 0.95
TC (mg/dl)	90.83± 1.34	129 .00±1.29	90.33 ±1.05	117.33± 1.88	102.00± 1.29	92.66± 1.10
TG (mg/dl)	99.83± 1.57	133.00± 1.63	99.00± 1.29	122.66± 1.49	112.16± 1.34	102.83 ±1.34
HDL (mg/dl)	24.83 ±0.67	15.50± 0.95	24.83± 1.06	20.16± 1.34	22.00± 0.81	22.66± 1.59
LDL (mg/dl)	46.00 ±1.15	87.83 ±1.77	50.00± 1.29	72.00±1.29	56.16 ±1.06	52.83± 1.34
VLDL(mg/dl)	19.16± 0.68	25.50± 0.95	19.16± 1.06	23.50± 0.95	22.50± 0.95	21.66± 1.49
SGOT(IU/L)	137.00± 1.15	152.00 ±1.29	137 .00±1.10	142.00± 1.29	139.16± 1.34	140.66± 1.10
SGPT(IU/L)	67 .00±1.15	82.00± 0.81	65.83± 1.34	75.00 ±1.29	69.33± 1.10	67.00 ±1.34

n =6 and p<0.01 , p<0.02 , p<0.02 , p<0.02 , p<0.01 , p<0.02 , p<0.05 , p<0.01 when compared to standard ; ANOVA followed by Tukey HSD test.

Histopathological examination

Staining of the control mice's liver in Figure:-4 reveals no structural abnormalities. Progesterone control mice showed mild congestion and localized necrosis in their hepatocytes, which were dramatically reversed in mice treated with sugoless at doses of 740 mg/kg, and 1480 mg/kg.

[Figure :-12]

[Figure:- 12] Histological section of liver stained with H & E- 100 X [A] Control mice [B] Progesterone showed mild congestion and minor focal necrosis in hepatocyte. However, [C] Orlistat (10 mg/kg) [D] Sugoless 740 (mg/kg) and [E] Sugoless 1480 (mg/kg) restored the hepatic architecture.

DISCUSSION

One of the biggest health risks nowadays is obesity, which is also a sickness of society. Pharmacotherapy and the required lifestyle modifications might be taken into consideration for optimal management. Fat is a complex condition, and there is already clear evidence that hormonal imbalances contribute significantly to the development of fat. A steroidal female sex hormone, progesterone is crucial for the menstrual cycle and pregnancy. Because of the accumulation of fat, progesterone hinders fat metabolism and causes obesity. Progesterone-induced obesity is a well-known model for evaluating a drug's ability to combat obesity. Polyherbal formulations are regarded as a safe and efficient treatment for a variety of diseases and lifestyle issues. As a result, the current study was carried out to examine the impact of sugoless formulation, a polyherbal formulation, in a model of obesity brought on by progesterone. Administration of progesterone is linked to an increase in food consumption and body weight. Subcutaneous progesterone treatment in the current investigation resulted in considerable rise in food consumption and body weight, which is consistent with earlier observations. In mice given sugoless formulation at dose levels of 370 mg/kg, 740 mg/kg, and 1480 mg/kg, we noticed dramatically reduced food intake and body weight. The active principles in sugoless formulation, which have been linked to a variety of therapeutic effects like hypolipidaemia, thermogenesis, and carminative, are primarily responsible for how it affects food intake. Weight gain in the liver could be a sign of hyperplasia or hypertrophy.

According to reports, the steroid hormone progesterone encourages the formation and storage of fats. The present study revealed considerably increased liver weight on progesterone treatment since the liver is a highly metabolising organ that is prone to fat deposition. The weight of the liver significantly decreased in mice receiving the sugoless formulation. It did not, however, result in any appreciable change in the relative liver weight. Progesterone is known to affect habituation measures including ambulation, grooming, and rearing. This progesterone impact could be brought on by gaining weight, which causes sleepiness and reduces motility. An open field test showed that progesterone treatment for 28 days dramatically reduced ambulation and rearing while increasing grooming in female mice. Significant increases of ambulation and rearing were produced when sugoless formulation was administered at various dose levels, whereas grooming was decreased. This effect is primarily caused by a drop in body weight and its subsequent impact on motility after treatment with sugoless formulation. The biochemical factors linked with progesterone treatment, such as blood glucose and lipid profile, reveal the impairment in fat and carbohydrate metabolism [35]. According to reports, hyperphagia caused by high progesterone levels in pregnant women increases the risk of gestational diabetes. Thus, the progesterone-treated group in our study saw a considerable increase in blood glucose levels, which were entirely reversed by the effects of sugoless formulation treatments at doses of 370 mg/kg, 740 mg/kg, and 1480 mg/kg. By stimulating lipoprotein lipase, which is responsible for the breakdown of dietary fat and promotion of fat storage in the body, progesterone altered a number of biochemical parameters in female mice. This resulted in a much higher blood lipid profile. Blood glucose levels rose along with other lipid profile indicators like TG, TC, LDL, and VLDL, whereas HDL levels dropped as a result of progesterone use. The levels of TG, TC, LDL, and VLDL were significantly lower in mice treated with sugoless. Sugoless oral treatment at different doses resulted in a notable rise in HDL values. The current investigation found that administering progesterone increased the levels of the liver enzymes SGOT and SGPT. These enzymes are a sign of hepatic damage or abnormalities when their levels rise. When compared to the progesterone-untreated group, a day therapy with sugoless (370 mg/kg, 740 mg/kg, and 1480 mg/kg) significantly decreased the levels of SGOT and SGPT. When compared to 370 mg/kg and 740 mg/kg, all of the data showed a significant difference in the sugoless 1480 mg/kg treated mice, indicating that greater doses are needed for the maximum anti-obesity effect. Orlistat 10 mg/kg, a typical medication, likewise exhibits superior results to the other treatment groups.[36]

The histopathological analysis demonstrates the drug's likely harmful effect on important organs. The liver segment from the progesterone-treated group showed focal hepatocyte necrosis and moderate congestion as deformed functional unit structures. However, sugoless (740 mg/kg and 1480 mg/kg) therapy restored the hepatic architecture. After 28 days of oral treatment of the polyherbal formulation, sugoless restored body weight, and the various ingredients caused changes in biochemical and histopathological processes as well as exploratory behaviour. The highest level of action was seen at a dosage of 1480 mg/kg. Due to its possible anti-obesity impact, it can be regarded as an efficient treatment in the control of obesity. Orlistat (10mg/kg) is used as standard in this study which provides us a better result as compared to all the treated group, but almost similar to sugoless (1480 mg/kg).[37]

CONCLUSION

Plants are one of the most significant sources of medicines. The significance of healing plants in improving human health capacity. Since the beginning of time, unpleasant and challenging situations have been widely documented around the whole world.

Secondary metabolites, which could serve as drug sources and are useful therapeutically, are common in medicinal plants. The use of plant extracts as therapeutic agents is growing.[38]

From all the observations, it can be concluded that the treatment of sugoless formulation may have been able to prevent the progesterone-induced obesity in mice. Sugoless (1480 mg/kg) performed almost equally as standard orlistat (10 mg/kg) in the majority of the studies. The sugoless might show anti-obesity activity through the collective effects of inhibiting adipocyte development, lowering serum lipid levels, and inhibiting fatty acid buildup in tissues.

Sugoless also demonstrated possible antioxidant activity. A little amount of the sugoless components used in a formulation demonstrated strong anti-obesity action, according to the synergy assessment study, which was better than the results obtained by using higher doses of the separate compounds. Additionally, combining the substances in a sugoless form eliminated any negative effects that each ingredient alone might have.

Thus, by increasing efficacy and lowering the toxicity of the substances, synergy on sugoless was generated. Sugoless, a novel polyherbal formulation, may therefore be useful for managing human obesity and its associated comorbidities, including insulin resistance and oxidative stress. Sugoless has anti-obesity properties, however a thorough molecular mechanism of action has yet to be studied.

Purified extracts that may be used for future research that will more fully characterize pharmacological and toxicological characteristics, such as a study of the mechanisms underlying the anti-obesity action. To fully comprehend the mechanism underlying this effect, more study was necessary.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors have no conflicts of interest to declare. All co-authors have seen and agree with the contents of the manuscript and there is no financial interest to report. We certify that the submission is original work and is not under review at any other publication

ABBREVIATIONS

WHO	:	World Health Organization
EMA	:	European Medicines Agency
FDA	:	Food and Drug Administration
FFAs	:	<i>Free fatty acids</i>
DNA	:	Deoxyribonucleic acid
NIH	:	National Institutes of Health
POMC	:	Pro-opiomelanocortin
TAARI	:	Trace amine-associated receptor 1
GABA	:	Gamma-aminobutyric acid
GI	:	Gastrointestinal
cAMP	:	Cyclic adenosine monophosphate
ND	:	Normal diet
HD	:	High-fat diet
DMV	:	Divya-Medohar-Vati
WAT	:	White adipose tissue
PCR	:	Polymerase Chain Reaction
DIO	:	Diet-induced obese
PHF	:	Polyherbal formulation
BSA	:	Body surface area
HED	:	Human equivalent dose
P.O	:	Oral administration
S.C	:	Subcutaneous
SGOT	:	Serum glutamate oxaloacetate transaminase
SGPT	:	Serum glutamate pyruvate transaminase
ANOVA	:	Analysis of Variance
HSD	:	Honestly significant difference

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